

eosc track

BUILDING THE

EOOSC
OPEN SCIENCE
OBSERVATORY

POLICY BRIEF

Monitoring Open Science across ERA: Early Lessons from the EOOSC Open Science Observatory

About EOSC Track

EOSC Track is a 36-month Horizon Europe project funded by the European Commission. OpenAIRE was a named beneficiary, pre-selected by the European Commission to lead this work and further develop the EOSC Open Science Observatory. Building on the foundations set by EOSC Future, the project will turn the EOSC Open Science Observatory into a complete, easy-to-use policy intelligence tool for policymakers. It will help support evidence-based decisions by providing reliable data on Open Science (OS) and EOSC policies, actions, and results at the national level across Europe.

This policy brief builds on Deliverable 1.5 of the EOSC Track project, presenting its key insights in an enhanced form.

Revision history

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Executive Summary

This policy brief^[1] aims to provide an overview of the strategic role of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Steering Board (EOSC-SB) in advancing Open Science monitoring within the European Research Area (ERA). It offers a mid-term reflection on the progress, challenges, and lessons learned from the implementation of the EOSC-SB's monitoring strategy. It highlights the strategic importance of two core instruments - the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science and the newly redesigned EOSC Open Science Observatory. These instruments together form the EOSC-SB's joint capacity for monitoring national progress, identifying gaps, and aligning policies with European priorities.

Key findings from the 2023 survey, based on responses from 32 countries, are benchmarked against the targets outlined in the 2022 EOSC-SB Opinion Paper. The analysis reveals encouraging levels of engagement but also underscores the need for clearer definitions, improved data consistency, and broader participation to ensure meaningful comparisons and policy insights.

The EOSC Open Science Observatory, enhanced as part of the EOSC Track project, now offers enhanced functionalities, including interactive dashboards, data export, and integration of multiple trusted data sources. Its co-creation with users and policymakers reinforces its role as a practical, policy-relevant tool for strategic decision-making.

Five key lessons have emerged from the monitoring process:

- A shared understanding of concepts is critical for data consistency.
- Targeted support mechanisms improve data quality and participation.
- Stakeholder involvement strengthens the usability and relevance of tools.
- Visualization platforms add value by making data actionable and accessible.
- Flexibility is essential, as targets and indicators must evolve with the policy landscape.

As the ERA 2025–2027 Policy Agenda introduces a more structured and impact-oriented approach to Open Science, this brief calls for a timely review of the original 2022 targets. Such a recalibration, grounded in practical experience and improved methodologies, will strengthen the EOSC-SB's ability to guide and support the coordinated advancement of Open Science across Europe.

^[1] This policy brief accompanies the policy briefing presented to the EOSC SB Subgroup on Monitoring on 23 June 2025.

Setting the Scene: Open Science Monitoring as a Strategic Pillar of the European Research Area

The objective of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide researchers and innovators in Europe with an open and trusted multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research and innovation. This is also reflected in [Heitor's report](#), in which the EOSC is considered a “key enabler of the digitalisation of research infrastructures while delivering the European Data Space for research data. It has the potential to become the most generally used infrastructure in Europe”.

The development of EOSC is steered by the Tripartite Governance, which consists of the European Commission, the EOSC Association representing the research community and the EOSC Steering Board (EOSC-SB) representing the EU Member States and Associated Countries to Horizon Europe (MS/AC). Specifically, the EOSC-SB has been instrumental in guiding and aligning national efforts with European priorities, particularly through its work on monitoring frameworks and policy coordination. The monitoring strategy of the EOSC-SB goes beyond EOSC and covers also other Open Science practices and enablers.

The 2022 Opinion Paper and the Strategic Vision for Open Science Monitoring

In 2022, the EOSC-SB expert group published an [Opinion Paper on Monitoring Open Science](#), outlining a coordinated and actionable vision to accelerate the implementation of Open Science policies at the European, national, and institutional levels. The paper framed monitoring not merely as an accountability mechanism, but as a lever to support and scale the deployment of Open Science practices. This is closely aligned with the broader ambition of EOSC: to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with a federated and open environment to share and reuse scientific outputs. The Opinion Paper set out clear short-term objectives for 2022–2024:

- Establishing a joint monitoring capacity to track progress toward Open Science becoming the “new normal” by 2030;
- Using analytical tools to identify policy and practice gaps, enabling targeted mutual learning and strategic intervention;
- Ensuring open accessibility of monitoring data to support transparency, reuse, and cross-country comparisons;
- Empower policymakers with evidence-based intelligence to align national policies with EU frameworks and investments.

This strategic direction was reinforced by a set of recommended national and institutional policies covering key areas such as open access, FAIR data, research software, skills, incentives, and citizen science.

To implement its vision for a joint and coordinated monitoring capacity, the EOSC Steering Board has established two key instruments: the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science and the EOSC Open Science Observatory. Together, these tools provide the evidence base, infrastructure, and visualisation capabilities needed to monitor national progress and policy alignment with EOSC and Open Science goals.

Monitoring withing the ERA Policy Agendas

The [ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024](#) firmly positioned Open Science and the EOSC as core components of a well-functioning internal market for open knowledge. The first policy action under this agenda focused on enabling open sharing and reuse of research outputs, including through the development of EOSC. Crucially, it called for the deployment of a monitoring mechanism to benchmark policies, investments, and capacities in Open Science across Member States and Associated Countries.

The subsequent [ERA Policy Agenda for 2025–2027](#) builds on this foundation and explicitly names “Enabling Open Science via sharing and reuse of data, including through EOSC” as one of the structural policy areas. This action seeks to bring about improvements across research communities and infrastructures in Europe by strengthening the legal, technical, and policy conditions for the sharing and reuse of research outputs. Importantly, the agenda includes as one of its expected outcomes the ability to “assess the impact of Open Science policies and practices through a dedicated Open Science policy intelligence platform”. This positions the EOSC Open Science Observatory as a key enabler of this ambition, offering a robust, integrated environment for collecting, visualising, and analysing policy-related data. In this context, the Observatory is not only a monitoring tool, but a strategic asset to support policy alignment, measure effectiveness, and guide future decision-making across Europe.

Concrete illustration of this position is the regular inclusion of data from the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science (and its visualisation from the EOSC Open Science Observatory) in the ERA monitoring system, notably in the ERA Dashboards [2023](#) and [2024](#). This underscores the growing importance of the EOSC SB monitoring activities as a trusted source for policy tracking and alignment across Europe.

Lessons Learned from the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science

The EOSC-SB Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science is the primary data collection mechanism used to assess national-level Open Science policy implementation, practices, and impact. First piloted in 2021, the survey has been conducted ever since, forming the backbone of the monitoring strategy. It is targeted at EOSC-SB representatives from EU Member States and Associated Countries to Horizon Europe and enables systematic benchmarking of national contributions across a wide range of Open Science policy domains.

The first lessons learned from the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science were shared in the EOSC Future deliverable [D2.2b – Mapping of EOSC Readiness of EU MS/AC](#), based on the 2021 pilot and the 2022 revised survey. This work, developed with the EOSC-SB, highlighted the importance of reaching a common understanding of key definitions, the value of the survey in fostering mutual learning, and the effectiveness of providing clear guidance and support to respondents. Despite increased complexity, the EOSC-SB demonstrated a strong commitment to the new monitoring framework. It was also acknowledged that both the framework and the survey would need to evolve over time. A key takeaway was the absence of defined impact indicators, leading to a recommendation for their future development, setting the stage for further enhancements in 2024.

In 2024, the survey was further enhanced with the introduction of a revised monitoring framework developed by the EOSC Track project in close collaboration with the EOSC-SB. The updated [Monitoring Framework for National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science](#) consists of 138 indicators grouped into 12 types of indicators across eight core categories, including Open Access, data, software, services, infrastructure, skills, assessment, and engagement. This framework provides a more granular and structured approach to monitoring, ensuring that survey questions reflect current policy needs and strategic priorities. It also allows for future revision, ensuring flexibility and adaptability as the European Open Science landscape evolves.

The delivery of the annual Surveys on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science is primarily driven by the EOSC-SB subgroup 'National Contributions to EOSC' (also referred to as the Monitoring Subgroup or Subgroup A). The subgroup's and EOSC-SB work was supported through the EOSC Future project, which concluded on 31 March 2024, and continued under the EOSC Track project, launched on 1 January 2024.

Figure 1: Monitoring framework for National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science

Data collection for the 2023 edition of the survey took place between 17 January and 1 July 2024, with responses received from 32 countries. The process was supported not only through direct coordination by the European Commission, but also through community engagement efforts such as the EOSC Survey Cafés, which provided a space for clarification and peer exchange during the submission period, directed towards the survey managers and contributors.

To benchmark progress, an analysis was conducted comparing the 2023 survey results to the targets set in the 2022 EOSC-SB Opinion Paper. The results of this comparative analysis are presented in Table 1, which illustrates national-level policy implementation and institutional engagement (full Survey analysis is available [here](#)). A similar methodology was used, and corresponding results can be found in the EOSC-SB Expert Group Progress Reports for 2023 (based on the survey results 2022) and 2024 (based on the survey results 2023), also showing the trends between both years.

Table 1: Progress towards 2024 Open Science policy targets (based on the 2023 EOSC-SB survey results) ^[2]

Policy	Share of countries having national or sub-national policy	National Target (MS/AC)	Share of RFOs having policy	Share of RFOs Target	Share of RPOs having policy	Share of RPOs Target	Share of countries having use cases	Share of countries having use cases Target
Open Access to publications	63%	100%	19.30%	100%	17.30%	100%	56.10%	100%
mandatory OA	24%	>75 %	N/A	>75 %	N/A	>75 %	N/A	>75 %
immediate OA	39%	>50%	N/A	>50%	N/A	>50%	N/A	>30%
Open data	54%	100%	16.30%	100%	6.20%	50%	41.50%	>30%
Data management	49%	100%	17.20%	100%	6.50%	75%	46.30%	100%
FAIR data	44%	100%	16.00%	100%	5.50%	100%	39.00%	>30%
Open Source software	22%	100%	0.90%	50%	1.60%	25%	31.70%	100%
Offering services through EOSC	17%	25%	0.00%	25%	0.20%	25%	26.80%	25%
Connecting repositories to EOSC	15%	100%	0.30%	50%	1.20%	25%	22.00%	100%
Data stewardship	22%	>50%	1.50%	50%	3.10%	25%	34.10%	>30%
Long-term data preservation	20%	TBD	5.70%	TBD	2.70%	TBD	41.50%	TBD
Skills and training for Open Science	37%	100%	3.90%	50%	2.50%	50%	58.50%	100%
Incentives and rewards for Open Science	37%	100%	10.20%	75%	3.30%	50%	36.60%	100%
Citizen Science	34%	100%	2.70%	50%	0.60%	25%	51.20%	100%

^[2] It is important to note several methodological limitations:

- The percentage shares are calculated using the full list of 41 countries, not just the 32 that responded, to maintain consistency with target definitions.
- For institutional-level indicators, the totals are based on the full set of reported organisations (4,857 RPOs and 332 RFOs), which vary across countries due to differing definitions and reporting approaches.

The lessons learned from the 2023 edition of the Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science reveal multiple good practices, including:

- Direct coordination and support from the European Commission and technical and expert support from EOSC Track, helping respondents navigate the updated survey format;
- The EOSC Survey Cafés offered an interactive space for addressing questions and promoting peer exchange;
- Enhanced usability features, such as the option to automatically reuse responses from the previous year and the pre-integration of data from external sources (e.g. OpenAIRE Graph, Eurostat), which helped streamline the data entry process;
- The broad involvement of national stakeholders in the 2024 revision of the monitoring framework, improved alignment with national practices and increased stakeholder ownership.

The EOSC-SB has demonstrated a strong commitment to monitoring activities, even as the framework has grown in complexity and scope. However, while participation continues to improve, there is still work to be done, of the 41 countries covered, 32 responded in 2023. As a result, current data may not fully capture the breadth of national efforts, posing limitations for comparative analysis and policy interpretation. Moreover, there is another challenge related to the fact that key definitions related to EOSC and Open Science are not yet uniformly understood across countries. For example, differences in how countries define and report research funding and performing organisations (RFOs and RPOs) lead to inconsistencies in institutional-level indicators. The EOSC-SB continues working toward a shared understanding to support more consistent and comparable data collection.

In light of these experiences, and considering the recent revision of the monitoring framework, it may be appropriate to reflect on the original targets set in the 2022 Opinion Paper. This reflection would not call into question the ambition or direction of the EOSC-SB's work but rather aim to ensure that the targets continue to be well-aligned with the evolving indicators and methodologies now in use. Such an exercise could support more effective tracking and policy dialogue going forward and reinforce the credibility and practical relevance of the monitoring process.

EOSC Open Science Observatory

The EOSC Open Science Observatory complements the annual Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science by offering a robust, digital platform for policy intelligence and strategic monitoring. As part of the EOSC Track project, the platform underwent a comprehensive redesign and rebranding, from the earlier "EOSC Observatory" to the enhanced "EOSC Open Science Observatory" (<https://www.eoscobservatory.eu>).

Developed with and for its users, the EOSC Open Science Observatory was shaped through interviews and regular feedback from the EOSC-SB Monitoring Subgroup and other key stakeholders. The involvement of the community in the co-creation of the EOSC Open Science Observatory has enhanced its practical alignment with national contexts and increased user engagement. This user-centred approach ensures the platform is not only technically advanced but also aligned with the practical needs of national policymakers, analysts, and Open Science coordinators.

The EOSC Open Science Observatory consists of two integrated components:

- **Public dashboard**, which presents interactive, comparative insights on Open Science trends and policies across Europe
- **Data management area**, including a survey tool to manage surveys, supporting data validation, and repository and tailored access for country managers.

The platform now includes significant new functionalities that streamline the visualisation of survey data and enable more dynamic interaction, including a download and export option that allows users to easily generate custom reports and extract data for use in policy planning, monitoring, and presentations. These visualisation tools unlock the full value of the underlying data, making it easier to identify trends, draw comparisons, and inform strategic decisions.

Crucially, the EOSC Open Science Observatory aggregates data from multiple trusted sources, including the above-mentioned annual EOSC-SB Survey, OpenAIRE Graph, national narratives from NOADs, and external sources like Eurostat and CoARA. This multi-source integration enhances reliability and offers a comprehensive view of the Open Science ecosystem in each country (see Figure 2).

To ensure data accuracy and trustworthiness, the EOSC Open Science Observatory applies a validation process. Survey data is reviewed by EOSC-SB country managers, while OpenAIRE Graph data undergoes multi-step quality checks, ensuring that all displayed information is verified, traceable, and fit for use in evidence-based decision-making.

Figure 2: EOSC Open Science Observatory data sources

In the near future, the platform will expand its capabilities with two new flagship features:

- **Country Pages**, which offer a holistic, country-specific view of Open Science ecosystems by integrating data from surveys, the OpenAIRE Graph, national narratives, and external sources. These pages allow users to explore progress, compare countries, and better understand national strengths and gaps.
- **European Open Science Resources Registry**, a curated repository of Open Science-related strategies, policies, guidelines, and best practices. Enhanced with AI-powered search, it helps users discover and apply relevant resources across the European landscape.

These enhancements will establish the EOSC Open Science Observatory as a central hub for Open Science monitoring in Europe, offering reliable, accessible, and policy-relevant insights that help shape national strategies and foster alignment with EU priorities.

Conclusion

The EOSC-SB Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science and the EOSC Open Science Observatory form the operational core of the EOSC-SB's "single joint capacity" for monitoring. They enable countries to benchmark progress, identify gaps, share best practices, and align national policies with European strategic objectives. As such, they are not just technical tools, but essential instruments for building a coherent, effective, and federated European Open Science ecosystem. Monitoring in this context is a learning exercise that aims to inspire and enhance the Open Science ecosystem.

The experience from this process highlights several important lessons:

- **Shared definitions are essential:** Variations in how countries interpret and report key concepts underscore the need for continued work toward a common understanding to ensure consistency and comparability.
- **Targeted support improves participation and data quality:** Tools such as the EOSC Survey Cafés, pre-filled responses, and expert guidance have proven effective in engaging stakeholders and streamlining the data collection process.
- **Stakeholder engagement strengthens relevance:** Involving national actors in the revision of the monitoring framework and inviting users to co-create the EOSC Open Science Observatory has enhanced its practical alignment with national contexts and increased user engagement.
- **Visualisation tools unlock value:** The EOSC Open Science Observatory adds significant value by translating complex data into accessible, policy-relevant insights and enabling data export for local use.
- **Monitoring frameworks must remain adaptable:** As indicators evolve and policy contexts shift, the original targets set in the 2022 Opinion Paper may require recalibration to ensure continued relevance and utility.

As Europe transitions to a more structured and impact-oriented monitoring approach under the ERA 2025–2027 Policy Agenda, it may be timely to revisit and refine the original targets set in 2022. Such reflection, informed by updated methodologies and practical experience, will help ensure that the EOSC-SB's monitoring efforts remain both credible and actionable, ultimately supporting the coordinated advancement of Open Science across the European Research Area.

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